

Deliverable 2.1

UNITA Online matrix

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Abstract

This document outlines the implementation of “the matrix” as the basic material used for developing faster recognition tracks.

The content of the matrix is gathered in a spreadsheet, available on the Datacloud WP2 folder.

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1. Framework

The application for the constitution of the UNITA - Universitas Montium alliance foresaw, from the outset, a set of tasks to be carried out by Work Package 2 in relation to Supporting the personalisation and recognition of study paths as follows:

With the aim of removing any obstacle to mobility the UNITA offices cooperate to prepare an online matrix matching recognizable activities and subjects in the three thematic areas offered at the UNITA universities for each academic year.

The contents of the matrix are drafted in cooperation with Educational offices, published on the virtual campus at M12 and cross-checked at least three months before the beginning of each semester. Issues concerning different levels of implementation of three-cycle education will be taken into account.

Thus, following the scope of the established tasks, the following strategic plan has been followed:

1. In order to identify the study programmes related to one of the 3 strategic areas - circular economy, cultural heritage and renewable energy-, each institution defined the selection principle for both the degrees and the subjects.
2. An extraction from the data base has been performed yielding the matrix. This matrix corresponds to the result of the task T2.1.1. It contains information exposed on an attached spreadsheet.

2. Matrix composition

In its first-year version, UNITA matrix has been composed following these principles:

1. Identify the Master's programmes in relation to one of the 3 thematic areas.
2. Identifying the Bachelor study programmes that lead to the above Master study programmes.

However, the relation that indicates whether or not a Master's programme is related to one a thematic domain was not clarified. The reason is directly related to the process of collecting the information:

- In some cases a questionnaire was sent to teachers asking them if they considered their Degrees belonged in the thematic domain.
- In some other cases, if the description of the study programme mentioned a key-word related to a thematic domain, the study programme was selected. But even by this process, the set of key-words related to a thematic field had to be undertaken by a relevant teacher. From one institution to another, the set of key-words may not be the same.

In the same manner, the rules for the selection of subjects differed a lot from one institution to another. A major obstacle was related to the data collection process.

The current matrix is composed by 532 study programmes and 2927 subjects. The details are given in Table 1, even though the content of the matrix is included in the attached spreadsheet.

Table 1: Number of entries in the matrix

	UBI	UNIZAR	UPPA	USMB	UNITO	UVT	Total
Bachelor study programmes	28	61	6	10	45	68	218
Master study programmes	42	63	3	20	68	88	314
Bachelor level - subjects	106	833	9	466	269	119	1802
Master level - subjects	71	129	11	600	244	70	1125

In addition to the standard information items (University, Faculty, Department, Study cycle, Name, ISCED code, Number of ECTS), the teaching language and the admission requirements are provided.

Some of these data items can be obtained directly from the syllabus. They will be used in the interactive cartography (T5.2.1) to identify recognition tracks.

Table 2: sources for study programmes and subjects

	Link
UBI	http://www.ubi.pt/en/courses#1o_Ciclo
UNIZAR	Bs : https://estudios.unizar.es/estudio/lista-ramas?tipo_id=5
	Ms : https://estudios.unizar.es/estudio/lista-ramas?tipo_id=6

	Link
	PhD : https://escueladoctorado.unizar.es/es/programas-doctorado-universidad-zaragoza
UPPA	https://formation.univ-pau.fr/fr/catalogue/toutes-les-formations.html
USMB	https://formations.univ-smb.fr/fr/rechercher.html https://www.univ-smb.fr/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/guide-interactif-formations-usmb.pdf
UNITO	https://en.unito.it/studying-unito/programs/degree-programs
UVT	Bs: https://admitere.uvt.ro/procesul-de-admitere/programe-studii/?sort=random& ciclul-de-studii=licenta Ms : https://admitere.uvt.ro/procesul-de-admitere/programe-studii/?sort=random& ciclul-de-studii=master

3. Further development

After having completed the work, the following issues can be identified:

- The current version of the matrix contains information related to educational programmes of the academic year 2021-2022. In some universities, study programmes have been updated and the current content of the matrix may be obsolete as of next academic year.
- The extraction of information items from the data bases must be done by an automatic computerised process. Especially if the matrix has to be extended to other thematic domains. However:
 - the institutions do not use the same digital tool for managing their educational offers. There is a strong issue about the inter-operability of the digital systems.
 - The selection rules or principles imply it is necessary to agree on a perimeter about what can be considered as related to a thematic domain and what cannot. This perimeter may differ from one institution to another.

- Additional information items have to be collected for the construction of fully tailored and flexible study paths that would be based on the prerequisite skills and knowledge and the learning outcomes of subjects. These information items do exist for some subjects, but not for all. However, it can be done only by the teacher responsible of the subject taught.
- An online version in the virtual campus has not been implemented because it would have consisted in redundant and extra work with respect to the construction of the associated cartography (T5.2.2)

Taking into account all these considerations, an additional effort has to be brought to pursue the activity related to the development of faster recognition tracks. The identification of successful study paths (T2.1.3) can be performed only after having overcome these issues, at least the two first mentioned above.

4. Related documents

Related Documents	Location
UNITA Study Programs	Datacloud\3_U_WP2\deliverables
UNITA Subjects	Datacloud\3_U_WP2\deliverables